

The spectrum of extinction rate magnitude: Supplementary Material

James S. Crampton¹, Michael Foote², Pete M. Sadler³, Roger A. Cooper⁴

¹ James S. Crampton. School of Geography, Environment and Earth Sciences, Victoria University of Wellington Te Herenga Waka, Wellington, New Zealand. E-mail: james.crampton@vuw.ac.nz.

² Michael Foote. Department of the Geophysical Sciences, University of Chicago, 5734 South Ellis Avenue, Chicago, Illinois 60637, U.S.A. E-mail: mfoote@uchicago.edu.

³ Peter M. Sadler. Department of Earth Sciences, University of California, Riverside, Riverside, California 92521, U.S.A. E-mail: sadler@ucr.edu.

⁴ Roger A. Cooper. Deceased. Formerly GNS Science, PO Box 30368, Lower Hutt 5040, New Zealand.

This document contains supplementary material in support of the paper “The spectrum of extinction rate magnitude”, published in *Paleobiology* and available at:

<https://doi.org/10.1017/pab.2026.10107>.

The CONOP Composite Dataset

For the present study, to avoid uncertainties and stochastic noise that result from low diversity and small sample sizes, we limit our analyses to species extant within the window 485 – 420 Ma and ignore species restricted to the intervals 491–485 Ma and 420–411 Ma. We round FA and LA ages to the nearest 1 kyr. We also eliminate 247 taxa that are restricted to a single level in the composite – taxa that are likely to be under-sampled (Cooper et al. 2014) – although their levels are used to constrain the shapes of the survivorship curves (see main text). Following these adjustments, the analysed composite contains 1742 species with FAs and LAs distributed across 1928 levels, giving an average of 1.8 events per level and an average temporal resolution of 34 kyr. (Note that, for certain cohort constructions, it is necessary to relax the 485 and 420 Ma limits slightly.)

Use of the CONOP composite sequence circumvents many problems in survivorship and extinction rate analysis, such as those associated with the discretization of time (e.g., Gibert and Escarguel 2017). Likewise, because the composite captures, in theory, the entire histories of all taxa in the sample, we hope to avoid some biases and edge effects that result from the use of finite windows of observation (e.g., Foote 2001). Problems in the uncritical use of survivorship curves to assess age-dependent extinction, notably biases that result from time-varying extinction rates (e.g., Pearson 1992; Hagen et al. 2018), are not of concern here because it is precisely these variations in rate that we are quantifying and that interest us.

Key Definitions

- *FA* and *LA* denote the times (in Ma) of first and last appearances, respectively, of a given species in the age-calibrated CONOP composite sequence; these ages are taken to be our best estimates of the ages of origination and extinction of that species (and see further explanation in the main text). Note that, because of the nature of biostratigraphic data, FA and LA events have different uncertainty behaviors during the compositing process: FAs will be correct or too late whereas LAs will be correct or too early.
- The list of *composite levels* is the list of all ages of FA and LA events resolved in the CONOP composite sequence. Each level has one or more corresponding FA and/or LA events. The composite levels are not spaced uniformly in time.

- **Birth and death cohorts.** A birth cohort is the assemblage of species that originated during a discrete interval of time; birth cohorts are used here for the construction of survivorship curves. A death cohort is the assemblage of species that became extinct during a discrete interval of time; death cohorts are used here for the generation of prenaissance curves. Compared with some other cohort assembly rules, birth and death cohorts have the advantage that each species is counted in only one cohort and thus extinction or origination rate data are logically independent for adjacent cohorts (cf. the “polycohorts” or “pseudocohorts” of Raup [1978]; Hoffman and Kitchell [1984]; Foote [2001] and others; and see Raup [1985] and Foote [2001] for general discussions of cohort analysis).
- A **survivorship curve**, as used here, is a graph in semi-log space that shows the number or proportion of species in a given birth cohort that survive to some future age. Going forward in time, a survivorship curve records declining **survivorship** and its complement, increasing **extinction**, of the cohort. The slope of the survivorship curve in semi-log space is the extinction rate (see main text).
- A **prenaissance curve** (Foote 2001), or “backwards survivorship curve” (Pease 1988), is a graph in semi-log space that, going forward in time, records the accumulation by origination – the “**accrual**” – of a death cohort (Hoffman and Kitchell [1984] use the term “accretion” for this process, a term that we do not favour because it implies layer-wise growth). Increasing accrual going forward in time corresponds to decreasing “**vacancy**” in the death cohort. The slope of the prenaissance curve in semi-log space is the origination rate. Prenaissance and survivorship curves are related simply by reversing the flow of time – a symmetry noted by Foote (2001).
- **pK-Ordovician** and **K-Silurian** denote two intervals of differing macroevolutionary regime (see Crampton et al. 2016); the boundary between these intervals is placed at the start of the Late Ordovician Mass Extinction event (as defined here), within the late Katian Age, at 447.5 Ma (see main text, Fig. 1, and Table 1).

Construction of Segmented Regressions

To fit the segmented regressions, we use functions “*segmented*” and “*selgmented*” in R package “*segmented*” v. 2.1-1 (Muggeo 2003, 2008), which allow the user to model the location of breakpoints and the slopes of segments between breakpoints. The method assumes

continuity between segments, an assumption that is necessarily obeyed in the case of survivorship curves. Starting with a simple one-segment linear model and one or more initial guesses of breakpoint locations, the method updates the breakpoint estimate(s) iteratively to eliminate discontinuities – gaps – between the ends of adjoining linear segments (for computational details, see Muggeo 2003; Lu and Chang 2023). In our analysis, for any survivorship curve, the fitting of segmented regressions proceeds via two steps: (1) automated identification of breakpoints, followed by (2) supervised refinement of these breakpoint estimates. These two steps are detailed in the following paragraphs. Note that in general, fitting of segmented regressions is easier for larger cohorts with more data; the minimum cohort size of 20 species, used here, is about the minimum for which segmented regressions can be easily fitted.

1. To obtain an initial estimate of the number of breakpoints (up to a maximum of 20) and their positions, we use an automated procedure implemented by function *selgmented* (Muggeo 2020) that employs the Bayesian information criterion to weigh improving model fit against increasing model complexity as breakpoints are added. During this stage of the analysis, breakpoints are first located at evenly spaced quantiles along the x - (time) axis, before iterative adjustment to eliminate gaps between regression segments. Initial, automated segmented regressions are shown in Supplementary Data File 1.
2. Given the modest size of some of our samples, the automated breakpoint identification of step 1 produces a relatively poorly resolved segmented regression for some survivorship curves. Hence, we re-run the model fitting procedure interactively using *segmented*, initializing the breakpoints (vector “*psi*”) using the results from step 1 together with visually estimated positions of any other conspicuous gradient changes in the survivorship curve that are not already captured. This step is iterated by the operator as necessary, adjusting *psi* each time using fitted breakpoints from the previous iteration and adding or removing visually estimated breakpoints depending on the shape of the fitted regression, until a “reasonable” fit is achieved, as evaluated by eye. Although this process of optimising the segmented fit is somewhat subjective, the need to prime the number and/or location of breakpoints is implicit in *segmented*, whether based on informed guesses or by simply placing breakpoints at evenly spaced quantiles (as in step 1). At the end of the supervised iterations, the breakpoints and segment slopes from the final model fit are saved for further analysis. In a few instances, because of

approximations in a segmented regression model, isolated segments are returned with slightly negative slopes; given that a survivorship curve is monotonic by construction, these segments are assumed to be horizontal and have their slopes set equal to zero for subsequent analysis and interpretation (although they are depicted with negative slopes on the cohort survivorship plots of Fig. 4 and in Supplementary Data File 1 – e.g., see cohort #3).

Assessment of Unimodality

The critical bandwidth test of Silverman (1981) is based on the fitting of kernel density estimates to the data, these being nonparametric estimates of the underlying probability density function. Here, “bandwidth” (h), refers to the window span applied when fitting a kernel density estimate; effectively, the bandwidth determines the degree to which the density curve is smoothed: increasing values of h indicate increasing levels of smoothing. For our purposes, the critical bandwidth (h_{crit}) denotes the point at which increased smoothing eliminates bi- or multimodality so that the density curve decays monotonically into the tail(s) without any local maxima. We calculate the value of h_{crit} using function “*bw.crit*” in package “*multimode*”, with parameter $mod0 = 1$ (Ameijeiras-Alonso et al. 2021).

Using h_{crit} , it is possible to test whether the true number of modes is likely to be greater than 1 (see Ameijeiras-Alonso et al. 2019, 2021). A number of such tests have been proposed; here we use a modified version of the simulation approach described by Wang (2003) to test the null hypothesis that the distribution is unimodal. This analysis is done in two ways. The first follows Wang and uses the observed slopes to simulate the distribution of h_{crit} . The second is an extension of this method that employs bootstrap resamples of the observed data; this second approach aims to incorporate stochastic uncertainties within the simulated distribution of h_{crit} that are related to our sampling of slopes.

The critical bandwidth test proceeds via the following steps:

1. For the n observations of extinction slopes, we calculate $h_{crit.obs}$ using function “*bw.crit*” in package “*multimode*”, as noted previously. For this step, and for the incremental and the segmented data treated separately, slopes are not partitioned into background, extinction events, or the LOME (unlike the histograms shown in Figure 3 and Supplementary Fig. 4).

2. If bootstrapping the data, we bootstrap resample, with replacement, n items from the observed slopes and calculate h_{crit} for this resample, which we denote $h_{crit.b}$.
3. A kernel density estimate is generated using function “*density*” (base R package “*stats*”) with a gaussian smoothing kernel and either bandwidth parameter $bw = h_{crit.obs}$ or $bw = h_{crit.b}$. This kernel density estimate represents our best guess of the smoothed density distribution that lies at the transition between a unimodal and bimodal distribution for the (re)sample of slopes.
4. A dataset of simulated slopes of size n is generated from the kernel density estimate of step (3) using the “*sample*” function (base R), and h_{crit} is computed for the simulated data, denoted $h_{crit.s}$.
5. Steps 2 to 4 are repeated 1000 times to generate 1000 values of $h_{crit.s}$. These provide an estimate of the sampling distribution of h_{crit} for our data.
6. We then compare $h_{crit.obs}$ with the distribution produced in step (5). The proportion of $h_{crit.s}$ that exceed $h_{crit.obs}$ yields an estimate of the probability that our null hypothesis is correct, where H_0 states that $h_{crit.obs}$ is within the range expected for a distribution that is truly unimodal. Conversely, if $h_{crit.obs}$ is large in comparison to the distribution of $h_{crit.s}$, then a large amount of smoothing is required to force unimodality in our kernel density estimate, the estimated probability is small, and it is unlikely that the observed distribution of slopes is truly unimodal.

Following the suggestion of Wang (2003), we also experiment with the use of parametric likelihood-based mixture models to detect the presence of distinct populations of slopes within our data, using the R package “*mixR*” (Yu 2022). For this, we assume that the data are described by a gamma distribution and reset all zero slopes to a small positive value (0.0001) as required for the gamma family of distributions. We do not report results from these tests for the following two reasons. First, *a priori* assumption of a particular parametric distribution is difficult to justify without theoretical underpinning and is difficult to test without assuming the absence of mixing; our trials indicate that results of mixture modelling are highly sensitive to the choice of distribution family (e.g., gamma vs Weibull). Secondly, for our data, mixture models tend to produce mixed populations that are very largely overlapping, so that any given population spans essentially zero to high slope values; this situation is not suggestive of distinct modes of low and high magnitude slopes (extinction rates).

Null Model Randomizations

The shapes and slopes of survivorship curves are influenced by the number of species present and their durations, the clustering of FA and LA events in time, and the ratio between the number of resolved time levels and the number of species and events, and these parameters interact in complex ways. For any given set of species durations such as the composite sequence used here, there is likely a singular, unique ordering and placement of those durations in time that yields the observed number of levels and distribution of FA and LA events across those levels. Any shuffling of durations in time will inflate the number of levels and reduce the ratio of events to levels and, therefore, alter the distribution of survivorship slopes.

Here we wish to simulate the shape of survivorship curves and the distribution of incremental slopes for the hypothetical situation of stochastically uniform and memoryless extinction rate through time, whilst preserving other attributes of our composite sequence and the graptoloid diversity history. To do this we randomize the position of the observed species durations in time but allow those durations to adjust slightly so-as to maintain the number of levels but also preserve the shape of the duration distribution. Our method employs an empirical, iterative process to derive each randomized model, as detailed in the following paragraphs. The randomized models – a suite of synthetic composite timelines of FA and LA events – are then used to generate survivorship curves and incremental slopes, as used in our other analyses. We do not generate segmented slopes for the randomized models because this is too labor intensive.

A randomization experiment, for a particular window of interest (see main text), comprises 100 iterations, and each iteration yields a synthetic composite sequence spanning an arbitrary 50 Myr. Iterations are primed using a sample of the observed durations of graptoloids that extinguish within the window of interest; the sample size is set equal to the number of species that extinguish within in the window, scaled to a time interval of 50 Myr (this parameter is referred to as the target number of durations, parameter n_{DT}). An experiment is calibrated to match three key attributes of observed data in the window of interest: the total number of discrete composite levels, scaled to a time interval of 50 Myr (the target number of levels, n_{LT}), the distribution of events per level, and the distribution of species durations. Here, “events per level” refers to the number of levels in the composite with one, two, three, etc. FA or LA events. Calibration of a randomization experiment is controlled using the number of discrete levels available to each synthetic composite (n_L), the number of levels constrained to have a single

corresponding event (n_s), and a minor adjustment to the observed durations (x_D). Each of these steps is explained in more detail in the following paragraphs.

Each randomization experiment comprises two stages: first, calibration of key run-time parameters to yield realistic synthetic composites (parameters n_L , n_S and x_D ; steps 1–7 in the following paragraphs) and, second, generation of synthetic composites and their survivorship curves, and calculation of incremental slopes. The calibration stage proceeds as follows:

1. A random sample of composite levels, L , is drawn without replacement from the universe of all possible levels, where this universe comprises all time increments at the temporal resolution used in the main analyses (i.e., 1 kyr). L forms the basic scaffolding of a stochastically uniform extinction history for a single iteration. The sampled universe spans 70 Myr in order to accommodate edge effects (i.e., it includes a 10 Myr sacrificial buffer on either side of the 50 Myr randomized composite). The sample size of L , denoted n_L , is estimated initially and modified iteratively in step 7.
2. At the same time, the pool of observed species durations is sampled with replacement to yield D , the set of durations specific to a single random iteration. The number of durations drawn in the sample, n_D , is set equal to $n_{DT} \cdot 70/50$. Durations in this sample are multiplied by a constant < 1 (parameter x_D ; typically $\sim 0.95 - 0.97$) to counter the effects of range extension that occurs during step 4, following, and to yield a distribution of randomized durations that matches the observed durations.
3. For each element of D , a random composite level from L is drawn without replacement and assigned to either the FA or LA. The age of the other, “floating” end of the graptoloid range is calculated by addition or subtraction of the duration.
4. Because the recalculation of range ends in step 3 creates many new levels in the synthetic composite, each floating end is then repositioned to the closest level in L that results in non-zero, positive duration. Although ranges are free to extend or contract a small amount during this process, in fact there is a net excess of range extension over contraction, a consequence of the fact that the duration distribution is bounded at zero. To counter this extension, we make the adjustment to durations explained in step 2, previously.
5. A subset of the levels assigned in step 3 is excluded from step 4, and these levels are thus constrained to have no more than a single corresponding FA or LA event. The size of this subset, n_s , is estimated initially and updated in step 7. This constraint is required

to ensure that the distribution of events per level in the synthetic composite matches the observed composite.

6. Steps 1–5 are repeated many times (here, up to 1000 trials) and the average number of levels in the 50 Myr randomized composite, n_{LA} , is calculated (levels within the 10 Myr shoulders are ignored), along with the distributions of species durations and events per level.
7. Steps 1-6 are repeated, adjusting n_L , n_S and x_D each time, until the average numbers of levels in the randomized composite matches the target, $n_{LA} \approx n_{LT}$ (Supplementary Figs 1A, 2A), and the distributions of events per level (Supplementary Figs 1B, 2B) and species durations (Supplementary Figs 1C, 2C) match the observed distributions within stochastic expectation. In practice, relatively few iterations are required to converge on a solution. On average, LA events are distributed uniformly in time – i.e., each experiment describes stochastically uniform extinction rate (Supplementary Figs 1A, 2A).

Once the optimal values of n_L , n_S and x_D are determined, 100 randomized, synthetic, 50 Myr-long composite sequences are created using the protocols described previously. For each of these randomized composites, we generate survivorship curves based on 1 Myr birth cohorts and compute incremental slopes, exactly as for the main analyses. Each randomization experiment yields > 500000 incremental slope estimates.

Sensitivity tests, not detailed here, reveal that the main results and conclusions from the null model randomizations (e.g., those shown in Fig. 6) do not change if substantially suboptimal values of n_L and n_S are used to generate the synthetic composites.

Comparison of Distributions Using Q-Q Plots

Q-Q plots and 95% confidence intervals are generated here using the base-R function “*qqplot*”. Because the different distributions examined have different numbers of data points, matching quantiles are calculated by interpolating values in the most highly sampled of the two distributions to the quantiles of the least-sampled distribution. Likewise, during computation of confidence intervals, sample size is determined as the number of points in the least-sampled distribution.

For consistency, Q-Q plots presented in the results are mostly configured to capture the 99th percentile, and axes do not span the maximum slopes measured; maximum limits are indicated for each axis. Because the slope data are so strongly skewed, approximately 50% to 80% or more of the data lie close to the origins of the Q-Q plots and much of the visual impact of the plots derives instead from the remaining, minor fraction of data in the upper quantiles (e.g., Supplementary Fig. 3). For this reason, Q-Q plots presented here tend to accentuate the upper tails of distributions, albeit, a visual emphasis that matches our particular interest in the steepest slopes and highest extinction rates. At the low end of the distributions, we note that some of the incremental data are zero-inflated to varying degrees, which results in local, zero “spikes” in some Q-Q plots (e.g., Supplementary Figs 3C, K). Given our treatment of zero slopes (zero extinction rates) as “real” data, we retain zero-slope quantiles in the Q-Q plots, although we do ignore these for calculation of multiplicative relationships (see next paragraph).

For pairs of distributions that display a multiplicative relationship, it is possible to estimate the scaling factor that transforms one of the two distributions to be similar to the other, such that the transformed Q-Q points lie close to the bisecting line (e.g., Supplementary Figs 3G, J). This factor is approximated by the slope of a linear regression through the untransformed data, and any additive shift is measured by the regression intercept. To estimate regression coefficients and because of the highly skewed nature of the slope distributions, we use MM-type estimators for robust linear regressions (Yohai 1987; Koller and Stahel 2011), an approach that is robust to non-normality of the data and the presence of outliers. For this step we also eliminate zero-slope quantiles that otherwise completely dominate the regressions and obscure relationships between non-zero values. Obviously, linear regressions become suboptimal in cases where one distribution is more skewed than the other, so that (part of) the Q-Q plot is significantly curvilinear (e.g., Supplementary Figs 3D, J, K). Regressions are computed in R using function “*lmrob*” in package “*robustbase*” (Maechler et al. 2024). The slope of a regression represents the best estimate of the multiplicative or scaling factor that relates non-zero y to x and, because of the strongly non-normal distributions, is more meaningful than relationships estimated from simple differences in the means or medians of the slope distributions.

Cumulative Extinction and Origination Probabilities

Cumulative extinction probability is calculated as follows (and see further explanations in Foote and Miller 2007: p. 190). For birth cohort i , and extinction event j :

$$P_{ij} = \log\left(\frac{N1_{ij}}{N2_{ij}}\right)$$

Where:

$N1_{ij}$ = the number of species of cohort i alive at the start of event j (calculated by interpolation within a given survivorship increment or segment, if so required);

$N2_{ij}$ = the number of species cohort i alive at the end of the event j (again, calculated by interpolation if so required);

For all cohorts that intersect extinction event j , the weighted mean of all P_{ij} is calculated as:

$$P_w = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^I w_{ij} P_{ij}}{\sum_{i=1}^I w_{ij}}$$

Where:

I = number of cohorts that intersect extinction event j ;

w_{ij} = weight for cohort i in event j = proportion of extinction event j that is spanned by cohort i .

Then:

e^{-P_w} = overall probability of survival to the end of extinction event j ;

$1 - e^{-P_w}$ = overall probability of extinction by the end of event j .

Origination of species was likely on-going during extinction events, and it is useful to compare cumulative extinction probabilities with equivalent cumulative origination probabilities. We therefore calculate cumulative origination probabilities for each extinction event, substituting data derived from death cohorts and pre-nascence curves into the equations given above.

We calculate cumulative extinction probabilities for all extinction events using both incremental and segmented slopes. Results using these two sets of slopes are almost identical for any given cohort construction: Pearson's correlation coefficients range between 0.98 and

1.00. For this reason and for simplicity, all results and conclusions relating to cumulative extinction probabilities are based on analysis of the incremental slopes. Cumulative origination probabilities were calculated only for incremental slopes.

For the incremental slopes, cumulative extinction and origination probabilities across the extinction events are similar between runs and key patterns do not change between runs (plots for separate runs are not shown here). Thus, for extinction probabilities, correlations between runs 1 to 4 are > 0.95 , and for origination probabilities they are ≥ 0.86 (Supplementary Table 1). Correlations for runs 5 and 6 are somewhat lower for extinction and origination probabilities, but are all still ≥ 0.65 except for a single value (Supplementary Table 1). Conclusions discussed here are based on the probabilities averaged across all six runs; there is no meaningful difference if we average across just runs 1 – 4: Pearson's correlation coefficients between the six- and four-run averages are > 0.99 for both extinction and origination probabilities.

Other Sensitivity Analyses

First, we find that slopes based on longer duration birth cohorts are lower than those based on 1-Myr cohorts, a result that holds true for both incremental and segmented slopes (Supplementary Figs 4, 8, 9). Differences between slopes based on 1- and 2-Myr cohorts are small and, although not statistically significant on Q-Q plots, likely to be real (Supplementary Fig. 9A – B). In contrast, differences between slope distributions based on 1- or 2-Myr cohorts and those based on 5-Myr cohorts are more substantial (Supplementary Fig. 9C – F). Multiplicative factors relating these different distributions are listed in Table 4 (rows 28 – 33); here we note simply that slopes based on 5-Myr cohorts are approximately half of those based on 1-Myr cohorts. In our results, it is clear that the longer the time interval over which survivorship data are aggregated, the lower the measured cohort extinction rates (Foote 1994). To a significant extent, this reflects the fact that the shape of survivorship curves is influenced by the number of originating taxa within a cohort (originating cohort size; Cascales-Miñana and Cleal 2012; numbers of taxa within cohorts are listed in Table 2), which is determined in part by cohort duration. This effect is visible even within slope data for just the 1-Myr, fixed-duration cohorts (Supplementary Fig. 10). Despite this cohort size effect, however, we find that multiplicative relationships between data partitions *within* particular cohort datasets (e.g., between background and extinction event slopes for 1-Myr cohorts) are more-or-less conserved

between cohort datasets (Fig. 8, Table 4, rows 16, 18, 20, 22, 24, 26, 34 – 51). Thus, although the absolute magnitude of slopes decreases with cohort duration, relationships between subsets of the data are, to a fair approximation, insensitive to cohort duration.

To explore the effects of originating cohort size further, we experiment with cohorts assembled using a fixed number of originating taxa, rather than a fixed duration. For these tests, we use a fixed size of 33 originating species, this being the median number of species in our 1-Myr, fixed-duration cohorts (runs 7 – 8; see Table 2). In cases where this 33-species threshold happens to correspond to a level with multiple FAs, then the multiple originating species are included within the younger of the two adjacent bins, so that some cohorts contain slightly more than 33 species and others contain slightly fewer (median and mean 33, standard deviation 1.5). The 33-species cohorts have median duration of 0.92 Myr (mean 1.30 Myr, maximum 5.74 Myr, minimum 0.42 Myr). Despite this cohort assembly protocol being very different from our main analyses, we find that multiplicative relationships between data partitions are, again, conserved (Supplementary Table 2, Fig. 8, labelled “33 sp.”). Likewise, relationships between data partitions and the randomized null models are also conserved (Supplementary Table 2, Fig. 8). These results confirm our earlier inference that relationships between subsets of the data are robust to cohort size and assembly protocol. Furthermore, as for our main analyses, the critical bandwidth test provides only the very weakest evidence for bi- or multimodality of the distributions of incremental slopes derived from these fixed sized cohorts (Supplementary Table 3).

Considering the randomized null models specifically, in comparison to the observed data, could the comparatively low slopes of the null models be due simply to differences in average originating cohort size? For the pK-Ordovician randomized model, the mean number of originating species in the 1-Myr cohorts is 25 (median 24, maximum 43); for the K-Silurian randomized model, the mean number of originating species is 32 (median 32, maximum 56). These values are significantly smaller than the observed 1 Myr cohorts (Table 2). Thus, in this case, the smaller cohort sizes of the randomized models should *inflate* the incremental slopes relative to the observed data and, if anything, the cohort size effect will weaken the signal that we report, which is likely to be underestimated.

Next, we note that our key findings are not dependent on the threshold of overlap required for the assignment of a slope increment/segment to an extinction event, which is set at 33% for our main analyses. For example, if we require increments or segments to overlap an extinction

event by 100% – i.e., to lie entirely within the extinction event – then the resulting distributions of slopes are nearly all close to, or statistically indistinguishable from, those of our main analyses (Supplementary Fig. 11). The only conspicuous difference is in the case of segmented slopes for extinction events, which are somewhat lower for the 33% overlap threshold (Supplementary Fig. 11D); that said, this difference does not alter any of our key conclusions.

Lastly, we wish to test for the effects of taxonomic practices in our data compilation and the possible presence of widespread, undetected pseudoextinction in the graptoloids – i.e., phyletic evolution that would reduce our species counts and extinction rates (e.g., see examples in Cooper 1973; Cooper et al. 1998; Urbanek et al. 2012; Whittingham et al. 2020). To do this, we use an automated approach employed in previous studies (e.g., Crampton et al. 2018; and detailed in Foote et al. 2018), whereby congeneric (sub)species are assumed to form part of a single, hypothetical, evolving phyletic lineage if the LA of one lies within three levels of the FA of the other. Putative “ancestor-descendent” pairs are linked recursively until no further joins are possible. This procedure reduces the number of species-level lineages by 26% and provides a rigorous test for the effects on our conclusions of widespread phyletic evolution within the graptoloids. At the same time, it reveals the impacts of changing taxonomic choices made during data compilation, i.e., whether particular (sub)species are regarded as synonyms or distinct taxa. Using incremental slopes for fixed-duration, 1-Myr cohorts based on these modified species ranges (runs 9 – 10; see Table 2), we find that multiplicative relationships between data partitions, and between data partitions and randomized null models, are similar to those for our main analyses (Supplementary Table 2, Fig. 8, labelled “Phyletic”). (Note that the randomized null models are re-calibrated here using properties of the modified data.) Yet again, the critical bandwidth test based on these modified data reveals that the null hypothesis of unimodality cannot be rejected (Supplementary Table 3). These findings indicate that our conclusions are unlikely to be significantly biased by subjective taxonomic decisions made during data collation or the effects of widespread and undetected phyletic evolution within the graptoloids.

Other Supplementary Material Files

Supplementary Data File 1.pdf: Example of cohort plots and segmented regressions for all retained cohorts in run 1. This file is produced during analysis with the supplied R scripts.

Crampton_Rscripts_Data.zip: Go to: <https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.vx0k6dk71>. Compressed folder containing R scripts and input files used for most of the analyses described in the main text and Supplementary Material. By way of example, it also contains additional input files required for run 1 described in the text, and associated output files. A “README” file contains further explanation.

Literature Cited

- Ameijeiras-Alonso, J., R. M. Crujeiras, and A. Rodríguez-Casal. 2019. Mode testing, critical bandwidth and excess mass. *TEST* **28**:900-919.
- Ameijeiras-Alonso, J., R. M. Crujeiras, and A. Rodríguez. 2021. multimode: an R package for mode assessment. *Journal of Statistical Software* **97**(9):1-32.
- Cascales-Miñana, B., and C. J. Cleal. 2012. Plant fossil record and survival analyses. *Lethaia* **45**:71-82.
- Cooper, R. A. 1973. Taxonomy and evolution of *Isograptus* Moberg in Australasia. *Palaeontology* **16**:45-115.
- Cooper, R. A., J. Maletz, W. Haifeng, and B. D. Erdtmann. 1998. Taxonomy and evolution of earliest Ordovician graptoloids. *Norsk Geologisk Tidsskrift* **78**:3-32.
- Cooper, R. A., P. M. Sadler, A. Munnecke, and J. S. Crampton. 2014. Graptoloid evolutionary rates track Ordovician–Silurian global climate change. *Geological Magazine* **151**:349-364.
- Crampton, J. S., R. A. Cooper, P. M. Sadler, and M. Foote. 2016. Greenhouse-icehouse transition in the Late Ordovician marks a step change in extinction regime in the marine plankton. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* **113**:1498-1503.
- Crampton, J. S., S. R. Meyers, R. A. Cooper, P. M. Sadler, M. Foote, and D. Harte. 2018. Pacing of Paleozoic macroevolutionary rates by Milankovitch grand cycles. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* **115**:5686-5691.
- Foote, M. 1994. Temporal variation in extinction risk and temporal scaling of extinction metrics. *Paleobiology* **20**:424-444.
- Foote, M. 2001. Evolutionary rates and the age distributions of living and extinct taxa. Pp. 245-294 in J. B. C. Jackson, S. Lidgard, and F. K. McKinney, eds. *Evolutionary*

- patterns; growth, form, and tempo in the fossil record. Chicago, The University of Chicago Press.
- Foote, M., R. A. Cooper, J. S. Crampton, and P. M. Sadler. 2018. Diversity-dependent evolutionary rates in early Palaeozoic zooplankton. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* **285**(1873): 20180122.
- Foote, M., and A. I. Miller. 2007. Principles of paleontology; third edition. W. H. Freeman, New York.
- Gibert, C., and G. Escarguel. 2017. Evaluating the accuracy of biodiversity changes through geologic times: from simulation to solution. *Paleobiology* **43**:667-692.
- Hagen, O., T. Andermann, T. B. Quental, A. Antonelli, and D. Silvestro. 2018. Estimating age-dependent extinction: contrasting evidence from fossils and phylogenies. *Systematic Biology* **67**:458-474.
- Hoffman, A., and J. A. Kitchell. 1984. Evolution in a pelagic planktic system: A paleobiologic test of models of multispecies evolution. *Paleobiology* **10**:9-33.
- Koller, M., and W. A. Stahel. 2011. Sharpening Wald-type inference in robust regression for small samples. *Computational Statistics and Data Analysis* **55**:2504-2515.
- Lu, K.-P., and S.-T. Chang. 2023. An advanced segmentation approach to piecewise regression models. *Mathematics* **11**(24):4959.
- Maechler, M., P. Rousseeuw, C. Croux, V. Todorov, A. Ruckstuhl, M. Salibian-Barrera, T. Verbeke, M. Koller, E. Conceicao, L., and M. Anna di Palma. 2024. robustbase: Basic Robust Statistics. R package version 0.99-4-1. <http://robustbase.r-forge.r-project.org/>.
- Muggeo, V. M. R. 2003. Estimating regression models with unknown break-points. *Statistics in Medicine* **22**:3055-3071.
- Muggeo, V. M. R. 2008. segmented: An R package to fit regression models with broken-line relationships. *R News* **8**(1):20-25.
- Muggeo, V. M. R. 2020. Selecting number of breakpoints in segmented regression: implementation in the R package segmented. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/343737604>.
- Pearson, P. N. 1992. Survivorship analysis of fossil taxa when real-time extinction rates vary: the Paleogene planktonic foraminifera. *Paleobiology* **18**:115-131.
- Pease, C. M. 1988. Biases in the total extinction rates of fossil taxa. *Journal of Theoretical Biology* **130**:1-7.
- Raup, D. M. 1978. Cohort analysis of generic survivorship. *Paleobiology* **4**:1-15.
- Raup, D. M. 1985. Mathematical models of cladogenesis. *Paleobiology* **11**:42-52.

- Raup, D. M. 1991. A kill curve for Phanerozoic marine species. *Paleobiology* **17**:37-48.
- Silverman, B. W. 1981. Using kernel density estimates to investigate multimodality. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society. Series B (Methodological)* **43**:97-99.
- Urbanek, A., S. Radzevičius, A. Kozłowska, L. and Teller. 2012. Phyletic evolution and iterative speciation in the persistent *Pristiograptus dubius* lineage. *Acta Palaeontologica Polonica* **57**:589-611.
- Wang, S. C. 2003. On the continuity of background and mass extinction. *Paleobiology* **29**:455-467.
- Whittingham, M., S. Radzevičius, and A. Spiridonov. 2020. Moving towards a better understanding of iterative evolution: an example from the late Silurian Monograptidae (Graptolithina) of the Baltic Basin. *Palaeontology* **63**:629-649.
- Yohai, V. J. 1987. High breakdown-point and high efficiency estimates for regression. *The Annals of Statistics* **15**:642-665.
- Yu, Y. 2022. mixR: An R package for finite mixture modeling for both raw and binned data. *Journal of Open Source Software* **7**(69):4031.

Supplementary Figure 1) Attributes of the null model randomizations for the pK-Ordovician. These plots are based on 1000 randomized, synthetic composite sequences that were primed using observed durations of pK-Ordovician species (and see Supplementary Material text for further explanation). **A**, Distributions in time of randomized composite levels and last appearance (LA) events (i.e., species extinctions); proportions are averages across 1000 iterations. Vertical dashed lines indicate limits of the sacrificial buffers at either end of the 50 Myr target interval; regions outside these lines are subject to edge-effects and have been ignored in subsequent analyses. As noted in the legend, the total numbers of species and levels in the randomized and observed target data are almost identical and within stochastic expectation. The plot demonstrates that levels and LA events are distributed uniformly in time in the randomized composites – i.e., extinction rate in the randomized data is stochastically uniform. **B**, Histograms showing the distributions of events per level in the observed and randomized data. The distributions and overall means are very similar, indicating that the basic structures of the randomized and observed composites are very similar. **C**, Histograms showing the distributions of species durations in the observed and randomized data. Again, the distributions and overall means are very similar, suggesting that the randomized data preserve key attributes of the observed composite sequence.

Supplementary Figure 2) Attributes of the null model randomizations for the K-Silurian; synthetic composite sequences were primed using observed durations of K-Silurian species. Other details and explanation are given in the caption to Supplementary Figure 1.

Supplementary Figure 3) Example Q-Q plots showing various features of the plots for both hypothetical and real distributions of data. On the Q-Q plots, the bisecting line of $y = x$ is shown in red. On panels (G) and (J–K), untransformed data are shown in black and grey polygons are the 95% confidence regions; if these regions exclude the bisecting line, then the null hypothesis that both samples come from the same distribution can be rejected at this level of confidence. In blue are the data following transformation of the x values as indicated on the figures; the additive and multiplicative elements of the transformation were estimated using robust linear regression fitted to the black points. For both the untransformed and transformed data, representative quantiles are labelled in red. See Supplementary Material text for additional explanation. A – F, Hypothetical examples and explanations of some characteristic patterns of Q-Q plots. “Observations” are shown as black points. The figured pattern for local behavior indicates a “spike” of identical values in x : the x distribution has a higher proportion of these values than y , and points in y are less concentrated or more dispersed than those in x . G, Q-Q plot of the K-Silurian background incremental slopes versus K-Silurian extinction event incremental slopes. Note that 80% of the untransformed data (i.e., the 0.8 quantile) lie close to the origin and the transformed data lie close to the bisecting line of $y = x$. H – I, Histograms of the untransformed and transformed data, respectively, shown in (G). Following transformation of the background slopes, the two distributions are similar. Note the log scales on the y -axes. J – K, Q-Q plots of the randomized data versus the observed K-Silurian background incremental slopes. Although the transformation does a reasonable job of shifting the data onto the bisecting line, the two distributions are clearly skewed with respect to each other and x has heavy tails relative to y (compare with E), so that the Q-Q points define approximately linear segments with distinct slopes. In addition, enlargement of the region around the origin (K) reveals zero-inflation: the randomized data contain a larger proportion of zero slopes ($\sim 80\%$) than the observed data, resulting in a spike in the Q-Q plot (and compare with C).

Supplementary Figure 4) Histograms of survivorship incremental and segmented slopes for runs 1 – 6 (see Table 2 for details of each run). Colored bars indicate proportions assigned to intervals of background extinction, the extinction events, and the LOME. Here, increments or segments are assigned to an extinction event if they overlap that event by one-third or more (see text). The numbers of observations in each category are given in the legends, together with the number of cohorts retained in each run. Boxes along the x -axis indicate grouping bins of the histograms. These data aggregated across runs 1 – 6 are shown in Figure 3.

Supplementary Figure 4) (Continued; caption on previous page.)

Supplementary Figure 5) Presentation of survivorship incremental (**A**) and segmented (**B**) slope data in a manner analogous to Raup's (1991: Fig. 1) "kill curve", showing sigmoidal relationship between log extinction rate (slopes) and cumulative proportion. The plots start at the lowest non-zero slope measurements (about 75% and 20%, respectively). Data are aggregated across runs 1 – 6. Inset panels are enlargements of the right-hand ends of the main plots, with points colored according to whether they lie within times of background extinction, extinction events, or the LOME.

Supplementary Figure 6) Q-Q plots for the distributions of observed survivorship segmented slopes, partitioned into pK-Ordovician versus K-Silurian (A) and, for each of the two time intervals, into background versus extinction event slopes (B, C), and extinction event versus LOME slopes (D, E). Note that, although the LOME falls within the K-Silurian interval, in (D) it is also shown for comparison against the pK-Ordovician extinction events. For these plots, our default segmented slope analyses, a regression segment is assigned to an extinction event if it overlaps that event by at least one-third. Other features of the Q-Q plots are explained in the caption to Figure 6 (and see Supplementary Fig. 3).

Supplementary Figure 7) Boxplots summarising segment durations for the steepest quartiles of survivorship segments (see main text). Median durations are given for each partition of the data and indicated with heavy lines on the plots. Boxes span the first and third quartiles (the inter-quartile range), whiskers extend 1.5 times the quartile values, and open symbols indicate outlying points. For each pairwise comparison, a nonparametric, one-tailed Wilcoxon rank-sum test is used to assess whether the right-hand subset has significantly longer durations than the left-hand subset: “ W ” is the test statistic, “ p ” is the one-tailed probability that the null hypothesis is true – that the two distributions do not differ in location. **A**, Comparison between pK-Ordovician background intervals and extinction events (including the LOME). The upper quartile of slopes was determined for the entire pK-Ordovician data partition, including the extinction events comprising the LOME. **B**, Comparison between K-Silurian background intervals and extinction events (including the LOME). The upper quartile of slopes was determined for the entire K-Silurian data partition, including the extinction events comprising the LOME. **C**, Comparison between pK-Ordovician extinction events and the LOME. The upper quartile of slopes was determined for just the segments assigned to the pK-Ordovician extinction events (but including the LOME). **D**, Comparison between K-Silurian extinction events and the LOME. The upper quartile of slopes was determined for just the segments assigned to the K-Silurian extinction events.

Supplementary Figure 8) Examples of survivorship curves based on birth cohorts of 1-, 2- and 5-Myr spans. As revealed here and in Supplementary Figures 4 and 9, as birth cohort span increases, in general the slopes of survivorship curves decrease. This is a function of the number of originating taxa within each cohort (Supplementary Fig. 10 and associated text). Extinction events are indicated with the shaded regions; for explanation of extinction event labels, see Table 1.

Supplementary Figure 9) Q-Q plots for cohorts based on 1- vs 2-Myr cohorts, 1- vs 5-Myr cohorts, and 2- vs 5-Myr cohorts. **A–B**, are based on aggregated slope data for runs 1+2 vs runs 3+4 (see Table 2 for details of runs). **C–D**, are based on runs 1+2 vs runs 5+6. **E–F**, are based on runs 3+4 vs runs 5+6. Other features of the Q-Q plots are explained in the caption to Figure 6 (and see Supplementary Fig. 3).

Supplementary Figure 10) The effect of birth cohort size – the number of originating taxa within the cohort – on mean incremental slope for a given cohort. Results are for just the 1-Myr cohorts (runs 1+2) and the associated randomized null models. The negative relationship between cohort size and mean slope is clearly evident. “ r_s ” = Spearman’s rank-order correlation coefficient.

Incremental slopes

Segmented slopes

Supplementary Figure 11) Q-Q plots for sample distributions of observed survivorship incremental and segmented slopes, partitioned into background extinction, extinction events and the LOME, comparing data in which increments/segments were assigned to extinction events if they overlap by 33% (our main analyses), versus those that overlap by 100%. Results shown here are for data aggregated across runs 1 – 6. For the incremental slopes, the assignment protocol makes negligible difference; for the segmented slopes there are some differences (and see Supplementary Material text). Other features of the Q-Q plots are explained in the caption to Figure 6 (and see Supplementary Fig. 3).

Supplementary Table 1) Correlations between cumulative extinction probabilities (above the diagonal) and cumulative origination probabilities (below the diagonal) for runs 1 – 6, based on incremental slopes. Extinction/origination probabilities were calculated for each extinction event for each run, and the values shown here are the Pearson correlation coefficients for the distributions of probabilities compared pair-wise for runs. In general, probabilities calculated for the different runs are very similar, although runs 5 and 6 show the lowest correlation coefficients. See Supplementary Material text for further comment.

	Run 1	Run 2	Run 3	Run 4	Run 5	Run 6
Run 1		0.97	0.98	0.97	0.78	0.73
Run 2	0.94		0.96	0.96	0.75	0.79
Run 3	0.86	0.93		0.89	0.70	0.79
Run 4	0.95	0.96	0.88		0.85	0.73
Run 5	0.75	0.70	0.79	0.68		0.38
Run 6	0.84	0.91	0.85	0.92	0.65	

Supplementary Table 2) Multiplicative and additive factors relating different distributions of incremental slope measurements for key sensitivity analyses. For details of the different runs and sensitivity analyses, see Table 2 and the Supplementary Material text. In all cases, the multiplicative and additive factors describe the transformations that, when applied to “Dataset 1”, will make its distribution resemble that of “Dataset 2” (see main text and Supplementary Fig. 3 for explanation of these factors). On Figure 8, runs 7+8 are identified with the label “33 sp.” and runs 9+10 are identified with the label “Phyletic”. These results should be compared with those for our main analyses given in Table 4, as indicated in the last column.

Time interval	Runs	Dataset 1	Dataset 2	Multiplicative factor	SE (mult. factor)	Additive factor	Figure	Row cf. Table 4
pK-Ordovician	7+8	Randomized data	Background	1.81	0.004	-1.66	Fig. 8B	1
pK-Ordovician	7+8	Randomized data	Extinction events	3.00	0.031	0.41	Fig. 8C	2
pK-Ordovician	7+8	Randomized data	LOME	7.54	0.282	0.04	Fig. 8D	3
K-Silurian	7+8	Randomized data	Background	2.26	0.008	-1.81	Fig. 8E	4
K-Silurian	7+8	Randomized data	Extinction events	5.06	0.039	0.02	Fig. 8F	5
K-Silurian	7+8	Randomized data	LOME	4.20	0.013	-1.88	Fig. 8G	6
Entire time series	7+8	pK-Ordovician	K-Silurian	3.09	0.017	2.80	Fig. 8A	9
pK-Ordovician	7+8	Background	Extinction events	1.80	0.042	2.26	Fig. 8H	34
pK-Ordovician	7+8	Background	LOME	5.07	0.085	3.75	Fig. 8I	37
pK-Ordovician	7+8	Extinction events	LOME	2.21	0.043	0.06	Fig. 8J	40
K-Silurian	7+8	Background	Extinction events	2.39	0.017	2.60	Fig. 8K	43
K-Silurian	7+8	Background	LOME	1.99	0.004	0.77	Fig. 8L	46
K-Silurian	7+8	Extinction events	LOME	0.79	0.008	-1.12	Fig. 8M	49
pK-Ordovician	9+10	Randomized data	Background	1.18	0.004	-0.64	Fig. 8B	1
pK-Ordovician	9+10	Randomized data	Extinction events	2.21	0.058	1.25	Fig. 8C	2
pK-Ordovician	9+10	Randomized data	LOME	5.57	0.081	2.84	Fig. 8D	3
K-Silurian	9+10	Randomized data	Background	1.92	0.014	-0.13	Fig. 8E	4
K-Silurian	9+10	Randomized data	Extinction events	5.28	0.110	3.00	Fig. 8F	5
K-Silurian	9+10	Randomized data	LOME	3.82	0.090	1.57	Fig. 8G	6
Entire time series	9+10	pK-Ordovician	K-Silurian	3.49	0.015	2.23	Fig. 8A	9
pK-Ordovician	9+10	Background	Extinction events	2.34	0.010	1.57	Fig. 8H	34
pK-Ordovician	9+10	Background	LOME	5.05	0.056	4.13	Fig. 8I	37
pK-Ordovician	9+10	Extinction events	LOME	2.16	0.078	1.34	Fig. 8J	40
K-Silurian	9+10	Background	Extinction events	2.62	0.053	3.46	Fig. 8K	43
K-Silurian	9+10	Background	LOME	1.97	0.005	1.78	Fig. 8L	46
K-Silurian	9+10	Extinction events	LOME	0.67	0.010	-0.51	Fig. 8M	49

Supplementary Table 3) Results of the critical bandwidth test for distributions of incremental slope measurements for key sensitivity analyses. For details of the different runs and sensitivity analyses, see Table 2 and the Supplementary Material text. The critical bandwidth test evaluates the null hypothesis that the overall distribution of slopes is unimodal. The “Observed h_{crit} ” denotes the critical bandwidth at which the kernel density estimate for the observed distribution transitions from unimodal to bimodal. The associated “Probability of H_0 ” estimates the probability that the observed h_{crit} is within the range expected for a distribution that is truly unimodal. Bold and underlined values indicate results that are statistically significant at the 5% level of confidence – distributions that may be bi- or multimodal. Abbreviations: “Boot.” = bootstrapped data; “No boot.” = non-bootstrapped data. As for some of our main analyses (Table 3), we repeat one test with a conspicuous outlier point removed, as indicated in the “Comments” column (“x” denotes a single slope measurement).

Run	Method	Observed h_{crit}	Probability of H_0	Comments
7	Boot.	79.79	<u>0.041</u>	
7	Boot.	25.71	0.197	Outlier at x=511 removed
7	No boot.	79.79	0.093	
7	No boot.	25.71	0.198	Outlier at x=511 removed
8	Boot.	24.22	0.254	
8	No boot.	24.22	0.154	
9	Boot.	29.09	0.235	
9	No boot.	29.09	0.322	
10	Boot.	19.13	0.410	
10	No boot.	19.13	0.443	